

ECOTOURISM RESOURCES OF JIZZAKH REGION

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Abstract: This article provides information about ecological tourism resources of Jizzakh region, ecological resources, ecological tourism opportunities in the region are researched with the help of concrete examples.

Keywords: ecotourism, ecological resource, recreation, nature reserve, places of pilgrimage.

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Uzbekistan is one of the countries rich in tourism resources. Among the types of tourism, ecological tourism is a type of tourism that is developing rapidly and has great potential in our country. Therefore, serious attention is paid to this type of tourism in the republic. Ecological tourism is a promising new segment in the tourism industry of our country, which has the opportunity to become one of the leading sectors of our economy.

The development of ecotourism, in turn, serves to develop the environmental protection system, preserve and protect biological diversity and unique natural areas, and increase the income of local residents. At the same time, it provides comprehensive support to the regional economy and is a promising market for investment projects.

That is why it is necessary to study socio-economic and natural-geographical factors in the use of nature and its resources in tourism. In the development of ecological tourism in Jizzakh region, first of all, it is necessary to make a deep analysis of the natural and geographical conditions of the region in order to register and describe the resources of tourism types.

Jizzakh region is located in the central part of Uzbekistan, at the crossroads of highways. The convenient geographical location of the region, favorable natural conditions, the presence of large water bodies, the uniqueness of the climate, a unique network of protected natural areas and unique landscapes open wide opportunities for the development and popularization of ecological tourism in the region. It should be noted that the region has not yet fully utilized all the opportunities to develop this field of tourism and turn it into a leading sector. To

preserve the integrity of ecological resources in the region and to fully use the opportunities in this area, it is necessary to pay attention to three main aspects:

- 1) ensuring full use of ecological resources by tourists;
- 2) protection of nature and environment;
- 3) preserving the traditional way of life of the indigenous population.

The existing unique nature of the Jizzakh region, its location in the heart of the Turkestan mountain range, and the beautiful and unique nature of the mountains, various landforms attract the attention of any tourist. The main part of the Turkestan mountain range is located in the territory of Uzbekistan and Tajikistan and stretches for 340 kilometers from west to east. The Nurota Mountains are the western continuation of the Turkestan Range.

The greenest corners of the region, unique natural landscapes, unique natural monuments are also located on the slopes of these mountains. Areas rich in ecotourism resources such as Kyzilmazorsoy, Kolsoy, Supa, Chortangi, Ettikechuv, Kashkasoy, Oriklisoy in the region of the Turkestan mountain range are surrounded by various natural juniper forests. It is noteworthy that the Zomin (formerly known as Ghoralash) state reserve was established for the first time in Uzbekistan in order to preserve the existing arboretums, increase the formations and protect the unique fauna. The total area of the protected area is 26.8 thousand hectares, of which 22.2 thousand hectares are covered with spruce forests. Zomin National Nature Park was established in 1976 in a part of the territory of the reserve in order to strengthen the protection of the beautiful and unique nature in the territory of the reserve and to develop ecological tourism. The national nature park is located in the western part of the Turkestan mountains, which is part of the Pamir-Aloy mountain range, in the territory of Zomin district. The total area is 24.1 thousand hectares. A very unique and diverse animal world lives in the protected area. 134 species of birds, 37 species of mammals, 39 species of reptiles have been registered here. Turkestan lynx, white-clawed bear, Siberian goat living in the territory of the reserve are included in the "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

There are many ecological corners of the reserve. Among them, one of the most attractive places is the high and strange-looking red stones located in the Kizilolmasoi area. These stones are composed of sand and conglomerates, which have formed different shapes and appearances under the influence of the natural weathering process. The local people call these strange-looking stones "Kyrgyz" because they resemble the human body.

In the middle part of Kolsoy, one of the tributaries of the Sangzor river, a strange gorge between limestones is called "Chortangi" by local residents. The word Tangi means a narrow gorge in the Persian-Tajik language. A difficult-to-pass belt between the mountains is called a stream bed, and water often flows through the

bed. The water gushes out of the gorge and makes all kinds of sounds like the birds. That's why this place got the name "Sayrovchi Dara". The gorge consists of limestone deposits, and its length extends to a distance of two kilometers. Such narrow and deep gorges are also present in the regions of Kashkasuv and Ghoralashsoy. Tourists are amazed by the fact that the palakhsa stones in the large arched part on the right side of Ghoralashsoy have been weathered for thousands of years and have various shapes, such as mythical dragon, tiger and other appearances. While watching the wonders created by this nature, tourists can enjoy the air of healing trees.

In the western part of the region, on the northern slopes of the Nurota mountain range, the Nurota mountain-forest state reserve was established in 1975. The main tasks of the reserve are to preserve a rare animal - wild sheep (Severtsov sheep) - arhar and walnut forests. Today, in the territory of the village of Mojarm, a very rare tree in the Central Asian region - the Eastern biota - has been preserved. This biota, which is more than two thousand years old, has a circumference of about 10 meters. Among the local people, there is a legend that when Alexander the Great came from the west and started marching to Ustrushona, he rested with his soldiers under this tree. Vadigan, Bogimozor, Ayiksoy, Boykongirsoy, Jum-Jumsoy gorges covered with birch trees in Bakhmal district of the region are also on the list of the greenest, unique natural landscapes of the region. The Sangzor river, which is the largest river in the region, and the Zominsoy basin, which starts from the mountains of the Turkestan range, have more than fifty springs with healing water and a calm nature. The north-western and eastern parts of the region are occupied by plains and low plains. In this area, the largest water basin of the region - the Aydar-Arnasoy lake system is located. In addition to being a unique tourist resource, these lakes are a habitat for wintering birds and an area with unique wildlife. The unique natural and cultural monuments in the province are sure to attract a lot of interest from domestic tourists and international tourists. This situation shows that there are great opportunities for the development of ecological tourism in the region.

It seems that the territory of Jizzakh region is very rich in ecological resources. But these resources are still not being used as much as they should be. Therefore, identifying, studying, promoting the possibilities of using existing ecological resources and building touristic places that meet international requirements will allow to increase the flow of domestic and foreign tourists several times. To sum up, the region ranks fourth in the republic in terms of abundance and variety of ecological resources, and second in socio-cultural recreation and excursion resources. Such opportunities indicate the need for intensive development of ecological tourism in the region, both domestically and internationally.

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